

SiC-ZrB₂ FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES PREPARED BY SPARK PLASMA SINTERING

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SUMMARY

Continuous SiC fiber-ZrB₂ matrix composites were prepared. The ZrB₂ matrix could be densified at 1600 °C by the application of MoSi₂, B₄C and C additives. The composites became brittle when the sintering temperature was at or above 1700 °C because of the damage of the BN coating and the SiC fiber.

Keywords: SiC, fiber, ZrB₂, composites, BN

INTRODUCTION

ZrB₂ has been recently considered as a promising candidate for the application at severe conditions due to the combination of unique properties such as high melting temperature, elastic modulus, hardness, electrical and thermal conductivity, good wear resistance and chemical inertness [1,2]. However, its rather low fracture toughness (3 - 5 $MPa\sqrt{m}$) has limited the fabrication of large components due to low reliability [3,4].

Incorporation of continuous ceramic fibers is one of the methods to add cumulative failure process [5]. Consequently, continuous carbon fiber-reinforced ZrB₂ composites has been recently intensively prepared [6,7]. However, carbon fibers in the composites suffered from rapid oxidation in air [8]. In addition, the strength of the composites were reported to be lower than those of monolithic ZrB₂ presumably due to the formation of cracks caused by the large difference of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) between the fiber and the matrix ($\sim 0/^\circ\text{C}$ vs. $5.5 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$) [9-11].

SiC fibers are highly oxidation resistant, and have a similar CTE value ($4.5 - 4.9 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$) with that of ZrB₂ [10]. However, due to the damage of the fibers during densification, reports on continuous SiC fiber - ZrB₂ matrix composites have been scarce [12,13], and the researches used large SCS-6 or SCS-9 SiC fibers fabricated by expensive chemical vapor deposition method (diameter: 148 and 78 μm , respectively) [14]. SCS-6 fiber has been reported to be too large for toughening of ceramic matrices [14,15], and the SCS-type fibers have problems for weaving because of the large diameter and consequent lack of flexibility.

Here we report the fabrication of continuous SiC fiber - ZrB₂ matrix composites using BN-coated Hi-Nicalon[®] Type-S SiC fibers (average diameter: 12 μm) by spark plasma sintering (SPS) method [16]. Milling condition of ZrB₂ powder was controlled for the homogeneous infiltration of the powder into the fiber spacings, and the possible mechanisms for the damage of the SiC fiber and BN coating above 1600°C were discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Commercially available ZrB₂ (grade: ZrB₂-F, Japan New Metals Co., Osaka, Japan, average particle size (d₅₀): 2.12 μm, oxygen content: 1.02 wt%), MoSi₂ (3N, Kojundo), B₄C (Grade HD20, H. C. Starck) and carbon (carbon black, MA-600B, Mitsubishi Chem.) powders were used as starting materials (79.5, 15, 4 and 1.5 wt%, respectively). The ZrB₂ powder was comminuted in ethyl alcohol by planetary milling at 300 revolutions per minute (r.p.m.) for 72 h using 3mm SiC ball and SiC jar. The resultant slurry was centrifuged, and the sediment was dried at 35 °C in vacuum for 24 h in order to minimize surface oxidation during drying. ZrO₂ formed on the surface of ZrB₂ powder was reported to suppress the densification of the boride [17]. The average particle size and surface area of the powder were measured before and after the milling using a particle size analyzer (1064, CILAS, Orlean, France) and BET (Autosorb-1, Quantachrome, Boynton Beach, FL), respectively. The oxygen, carbon and silicon content of the powder was analyzed using an inert gas carrying melting-infrared absorptiometer (TC-600, Leco, St. Joseph, MI), an induction heating-infrared absorptiometer (CS 444-LS, Leco, St. Joseph, MI) and SiO₂ gravimetric method, respectively.

The pulverized ZrB₂ powder was mixed with MoSi₂, B₄C and C additives (15, 4, 1.5 wt%, respectively) in ethyl-alcohol at 200 r.p.m. for 8 h using a planetary mill. The mixed slurry was dried and sieved (mesh size: 120 μm).

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, PHI Quantera SXM, ULVAC PHI, Chigasaki, Japan) analysis was performed before and after the wet processing of ZrB₂ powder in water or ethyl alcohol in order to understand surface corrosion behavior of the powder. XPS spectra of Zr 3d_(5/2,3/2), B 1s and O 1s were measured by using monochromitized Al K α radiation.

Continuous Hi-Nicalon[®] Type-S SiC fibers having BN coating were aligned into one-dimension and were embedded into the powder mixture which was placed in a carbon mold. Then, the mold containing the powder and fibers was heated at 1600 – 1750 °C under a uni-axial pressure of 40 MPa in vacuum using a spark-plasma sintering furnace (SPS, Dr. Sinter SCM 3000, Sumitomo Coal Mining Co. Ltd., heating within 3 min from 600 °C to the sintering temperature). The heating rate was reduced during the last 50 °C (50 °C/min) in order to prevent the overshoot of temperature.

After sintering, the density of the specimens was analyzed using Archimedes' method. The theoretical density of ZrB₂, MoSi₂, B₄C and C used for the calculation of the relative density by rule of mixture was 6.01, 6.31, 2.5 and 1.95 g/cm³, respectively [18].

The sintered specimens were machined into bars (2 × 2 × 15 mm) and were fractured by impacting using a metallic pin. Polished cross-section and fractured surface of the composite were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-6700F, JEOL).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the properties of ZrB₂ powder before and after planetary milling for 72 h. The increase of oxygen content during the milling was due to the formation of ZrO₂ or Zr-OH on the surface of the boride powder by the reaction with H₂O and/or oxygen which dissolved in ethyl alcohol [19-21]. The reaction also induced the formation of H₃BO₃, which was, however, mostly dissolved in the dispersoid due to high solubility [22]. Carbon and Si in the milled powder were mostly originated from SiC ball and jar. The amount of SiC incorporated in the milled ZrB₂ powder was estimated to be 3.7 wt% from the Si content (Table 1).

Table 1. Chemical composition, average particle size (d_{50}) and surface area of ZrB₂ powder before and after the planetary milling at 300 r.p.m. for 72 h.

	O (wt%)	C (wt%)	Si (wt%)	d_{50} (μm)	BET (m^2/g)
As received	1.0 \pm 0.1	0.3 \pm 0.1	<0.05	2.34	1.29
After milling	2.7 \pm 0.1	1.7 \pm 0.1	2.6 \pm 0.05	0.54	10.05

Lange *et al.* reported that the ratio between the size of filler particle (d_p) and fiber diameter ($2r_f$) should be $d_p/2r_f < 0.05$ in order to guarantee the homogeneous filling of particles at the interstices of fibers [23]. Because the average diameter of the Hi-Nicalon[®] Type-S fiber was reported to be 12 μm [14], the appropriate size of ZrB₂ powder for the fabrication of SiC fiber - ZrB₂ matrix composites is considered to be smaller than 0.6 μm . In a previous research, the present authors reported that pulverization of ZrB₂ powder to sub-micrometer in size was difficult after an intensive planetary milling for 72 h at 180 – 200 r.p.m. using large SiC balls (10 mm) [24]. The high Young's modulus (489 GPa) and moderate fracture toughness ($3.5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$) of ZrB₂ were considered as the main reasons for the difficulty of pulverization [4]. However, Table 1 and Figure 1 clearly indicate that fine ZrB₂ powder (d_{50} : 0.54 μm) was obtained by using small SiC ball (3 mm) and by increasing rotation speed to 300 r.p.m. The bimodal size distribution of the as-received ZrB₂ powder changed into

Figure 1. Morphology and size distribution of ZrB₂ powder (a) before and (b) after the planetary milling at 300 r.p.m. for 72 h using 3 mm SiC ball.

monomodal shape after the milling. The surface area of the pulverized powder was 10.05 m²/g.

Surface of ZrB₂ powder was mainly composed of Zr-OH after a milling in ethyl alcohol for 72 h, but Zr-B bonding remained on the powder surface (Figure 2). Total oxygen content in the powder increased by the milling process, but the average thickness of oxide layer at the powder surface decreased after the milling due to the formation of fresh surface (Table 2) [21].

Figure 2. XPS data of (a) pristine ZrB₂ powder (b) after static ageing in water at pH 7 for 240 h (c) after milling for 72 h in ethyl alcohol

Table 2. Ratio of the maximum peak intensity between Zr-B and Zr-O (Zr 3d_{5/2}) in the XPS spectra.

	Pristine powder	After aging for 240 h in water at pH 7	After milling for 72 h in ethyl alcohol
Zr-B/Zr-O	0.37	0.36	0.42

The deformation and damage of the Hi-Nicalon[®] Type-S fiber were reported to occur at 1750 °C during the fabrication of fiber-reinforced composites by hot pressing [16,25]. Consequently, the present authors developed an additive system (15 wt% MoSi₂ + 4 wt% B₄C + 1.5 wt% carbon) and could obtain dense ZrB₂ by SPS at 1600 °C under 40 MPa pressure in vacuum [26]. The decrease of the melting temperature of MoSi₂ by B₄C and the suppression of ZrB₂ grain growth by carbon were considered as the main reasons for the low-temperature sintering [26]. Figure 3 shows the polished cross-section of the composites densified at 1600 °C, 1700 °C and 1750 °C. Dense ZrB₂ matrices were observed regardless of the sintering temperature. The black spots in the matrices were MoSi₂ and carbon [26]. The relative density of the composite sintered at 1600, 1700 and 1750 °C was 96.2, 97.5 and 97.5 %, respectively. The deformation of the fibers was not clearly observed in Fig. 2 after sintering at 1600 °C and 1700 °C for 10 min. On the other hand, the cross-sectional aspect ratio of the fibers increased by the pressure applied during SPS when the sintering temperature was 1750 °C (Figure 3 (c)),

indicating that the deformation of the Hi-Nicalon[®] Type-S fibers became distinct at this condition.

Figure 3. Polished cross-section of SiC fiber - ZrB₂ matrix composites densified with 40 MPa pressure in vacuum at (a) 1600 °C for 10 min, (b) 1700 °C for 10 min and (c) 1600 °C for 10 min and subsequently at 1750 °C for 1 min.

The control of bonding strength and frictional sliding between fiber and matrix is a key factor for the pull-out of fibers in fiber-reinforced ceramic composites. BN coating induces weak bonding between the fiber and the matrix and behaves as a solid lubricant, thus promotes fiber pull-out during the fracture of ceramic composites [25]. Pulled-out fibers were observed at the fractured surface of the CMC sintered at 1600 °C (Figure 4 (a)). The cracks mainly propagated through the outside of the BN coating. As a result, the coating was attached on the surface of the exposed fibers (Figure 4 (b)). The exposed coating was very smooth, indicating that the damage of the BN coating did not distinctly occur at 1600 °C. The composites sintered at 1700 °C for 10 min. showed rather brittle fracture behavior (Figure 4 (c)), although the fibers could be identified at the fractured surface. The surface roughness of the fibers in the CMC increased compared to those sintered at 1600 °C (Figure 4 (b), (d)). Pulled-out fibers were not

clearly observed in the composites fabricated at 1750 °C (Figure 4 (e)). The surface of the fibers was very rough and particles were adhered on it (Figure 4 (f)).

Figure 4. Fractured surface of SiC fiber - ZrB₂ matrix composites densified at (a), (b) 1600 °C for 10 min, (c), (d) 1700 °C for 10 min and (e), (f) 1600 °C for 10 min and subsequently at 1750 °C for 1 min. (magnification: (a), (c), (e): ×500, (b), (d), (f): ×2,000).

The magnified view of the fiber-matrix interface clearly demonstrates that the BN coating and the fibers were not deteriorated in the CMC densified at 1600 °C (Figure 5 (a)). The thickness of the BN coating was ~200 nm. In contrast, although macroscopic deformation of the fiber was not clearly observed in the specimens sintered at 1700 °C (Figure 3 (b)), the BN coating and the fiber were damaged. Direct contact between the fiber and the matrix due to the removal of the coating was also observed. The BN coating was heavily damaged in the composites prepared at 1750 °C. The deterioration of the fiber surface, as well as the macroscopic deformation of the fiber, were clearly identified (Figure 3 (c), Figure 5 (b)).

Figure 5. Microstructure of SiC fiber - ZrB₂ matrix composites densified at (a) 1600 °C for 10 min, (b) 1600 °C for 10 min and subsequently at 1750 °C for 1 min.

Several mechanisms can be considered to explain the damage of BN coating at and above 1700 °C. First, during densification ZrB₂ grains in the matrix might grow into the rather soft BN layer, which caused the damage of the BN coating [25]. Growth of ZrB₂ grains was evident with increasing temperature (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Microstructure of ZrB₂ sintered with 7.5wt% MoSi₂ + 4wt% B₄C sintered in vacuum under 40 MPa pressure at (a) 1600°C for 10 min, (b) 1750°C for 1 min.

The chemical reactions between BN and the other constituents are considered as another reason. The thermo-chemical data of the components were obtained from a reference [27]. The reactions between BN and the other non-oxide constituents such as;

are not probable up to 1750 °C. However, ZrO₂, which generally formed on the surface of ZrB₂, is believed to cause the following decomposition reactions;

The logarithm of the equilibrium constant (Log K) of reaction (3) and (4) became positive above 1792 °C and 1587°C, respectively, indicating that the BN coating reacted with ZrO₂, B₄C and carbon during densification mainly by reaction (4). The reaction is believed to become intensive at and above 1700 °C when considering the rapid increase of the Log K value above 1600 °C. The loss of BN layer (Figure 5 (b)) and the adhesion of particles on the surface of the fibers (Figure 4 (f)) were most probably caused by chemical reactions such as reaction (4).

B₂O₃, which formed together with ZrO₂ by the surface corrosion of ZrB₂ [21], also induced the damage of the coating layer because BN partly dissolves in molten B₂O₃. The solubility limit was reported to be 0.2 anion% N at 1250 °C [28].

The above discussion indicates that the damage of BN coating was mainly caused by oxides, and may be suppressed by minimizing the surface corrosion of ZrB₂ powder.

CONCLUSIONS

Fine ZrB₂ powders which were appropriate for the fabrication of SiC fiber - ZrB₂ matrix composites could be obtained by the optimization of milling parameters. The average particle size of the pulverized powder was 0.54 μm. Dense fiber-reinforced composites containing fine SiC fibers (diameter: 12 μm) were obtained after spark-plasma sintering at 1600 °C for 10 minutes by the application of 15 wt% MoSi₂, 4wt% B₄C and 1.5 wt% carbon additives. The damage of the fiber or BN coating did not distinctly occur at 1600 °C and pulled-out fibers were observed at the fractured surface of the CMC. On the other hand, reactions occurred between the constituents when sintering at and above 1700 °C and the resultant composites exhibited brittle fracture. ZrO₂ and B₂O₃, which formed on the surface of ZrB₂ powder by surface corrosion, promoted the damage of the BN coating during the densification of the composites.

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